

Supporting information

MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ nanorods synthesized using NiO nanoparticles for hydrogen evolution in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis

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Figure S1: The equivalent circuit - L (H) (inductance of connecting cables), R2 (Ω) (system resistivity), R1 and R3 (Ω) (polarisation resistance), CPE (constant phase element), R4 - resistance of liquid electrolyte in Ni foam pores, C1 (F) - capacity of the double layer on the pore walls of the Ni foam.

Figure S2: STEM images and elemental mapping of NiMoO₄ precursor b) Mo, c) Ni, d) O.

Figure S3: TEM micrograph (bright field) of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C).

Figure S4: TEM bright field of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ a) 500 °C and b) 600 °C.

Table S1: Elemental NiMoO₄ composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	9.3%	9.6%	81.2%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.7	4.4

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo.

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	0.97	1.03	0.11	0.12	0.23

Table S2: Elemental MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (500 °C) composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	10.1%	2.4%	88.74%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.2	4.3

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	4.15	0.24	0.12	0.03	0.14

Table S3: Elemental $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) composition obtained by XPS

	Mo	Ni	O
Element Percentage	10.9%	5.0%	84.1%
Experimental stoichiometry ^a	1	0.3	3.8

^a Experimental stoichiometry normalised to Mo

	Mo/Ni	Ni/Mo	Mo/O	Ni/O	Mo+Ni/O
Experimental elements ratio	2.20	0.45	0.13	0.06	0.19

Table S4: composition (%) relative to the different oxidation states of Mo by XPS.

	Mo (0) %	Mo (IV) %	Mo (V) %	Mo (VI) %
$\text{NiMoO}_4/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ (previous work)	2.6	28	8.3	61
NiMoO_4	-	-	4	-
$\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ 500 °C (previous work)	22.2	57.9	16.5	3.4
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C)	0	7	35	58
$\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ 600 °C (previous work)	17.1	65.9	13.9	3.1
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C)	1	36	9	54

Figure S5: a) Comparison spectra of bare NiO nanopowder then MoNiO₄ precursor grown onto NiO and MoNiO₄/Ni foam from previous work [1]. b) Comparison spectra of MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 500 °C and MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C.

Figure S6: Comparison between MoO₂/Ni_{foam} 600 °C (previous work) and MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C). LSV registered at 1 mV s⁻¹ @ 1600 rpm, 0.1 M KOH.

Figure S7: Nyquist plot for a) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and b) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), recorded at different potentials.

Figure S8: fit results for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ ($600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) at -0.1 V vs RHE .

Element	Freedom	Value	Error	Error %
R1	Fixed(X)	37	N/A	N/A
R2	Fixed(X)	4,9	N/A	N/A
CPE1-T	Fixed(X)	0,0002551	N/A	N/A
CPE1-P	Fixed(X)	0,8	N/A	N/A
R3	Free(+)	134,5	2,4759	1,8408
CPE2-T	Free(+)	0,0019835	8,9794E-05	4,527
CPE2-P	Free(+)	0,84953	0,01467	1,7268

Figure S9: Equivalent circuit for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) at -0.1 V vs RHE with relative circuital elements values.

Figure S10: Nyquist plots of the EIS measurements using the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode and anodes with IrO_2 or NiCo_2O_4 catalysts respectively. EIS measured in the frequency range 100 kHz–10Hz, with maximal amplitude 10 mV at cell voltage 1.6 V

Table S5: Performance comparison of literature AEMWE data with Ni-Mo cathodes

Anion Exchange Membrane	Anion Exchange Ionomer	Cathode Catalyst	Anode catalyst	Electrolyte	Cell temp. °C	A cm ⁻² @ Vcell	Durability data	Ref.
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ -xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	Ni foam	1 M KOH @ anode	60	0.82 @2	50 h 1 A cm ⁻²	this work
FAA-3-PK-130	--	MoO ₂ /Ni	Fe-MoNi/Ni	1 M KOH @anode	60	0.55 @2	300 h 0.5 A cm ⁻²	previous work [1]
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	IrO ₂	1 M KOH	50	0.9@1.8		this work
FAA-3-PK-130	Fumasep FAA-3-film	MoO ₃ xNiMoO ₄ (600 °C)	NiCoO ₄	1 M KOH	50	1.0@2.0		this work
PTFE-Sustainion	Nafion	Ni-Mo	Fe-Ni-Mo	1 M KOH @cathode	80	1.0 @1.57	--	[2]
FAA-3-50	FAA3	NiMo/K ^B	NiFe (85:15 at.%)	1 M KOH @anode	50	1.0 @1.8	2000 h 1 A cm ⁻²	[3]
PVBC-MPy/35%P EK-cardo	--	Ni-Mo	Ni-Fe	1 M KOH	60	0.5 @2	42 h 0.5 A cm ⁻²	[4]
FAA-3-PK-130	--	MoNi/NiMoO _x	Co ₂ (OH) ₃ Cl/FeOOH	1 M KOH	25	0.5 @ 3.05	1600 h 0.2 A cm ⁻²	[5]
Sustainion® X37-50	--	NiMo/TP-4	NiFe/TP-4	1 M KOH	50	--	100 h 1 A cm ⁻²	[6]
PFTP-13	--	20 mg cm ⁻² Ni-Fe	20 mg cm ⁻² Ni-Fe	1 M KOH cathode	80	1.6 @2.0	1000 h, 0.5 A cm ⁻² , 60 C, no degr	[7]

References:

- [1] F. Bartoli, L. Capozzoli, T. Peruzzolo, M. Marelli, C. Evangelisti, K. Bouzek, J. Hnát, G. Serrano, L. Poggini, K. Stojanovski, V. Briega-Martos, S. Cherevko, H. A. Miller, F. Vizza, *J Mater Chem A Mater* **2023**, DOI 10.1039/D2TA09339A.
- [2] P. Chen, X. Hu, *Adv Energy Mater* **2020**, *10*, 2002285.
- [3] S. Campagna Zignani, M. Lo Faro, A. Carbone, C. Italiano, S. Trocino, G. Monforte, A. S. Aricò, *Electrochim Acta* **2022**, *413*, 140078.
- [4] H. Li, M. R. Kraglund, A. K. Reumert, X. Ren, D. Aili, J. Yang, *J Mater Chem A Mater* **2019**, *7*, 17914.
- [5] X. Shi, X. Zheng, H. Wang, H. Zhang, M. Qin, B. Lin, M. Qi, S. Mao, H. Ning, R. Yang, L. Xi, Y. Wang, *Adv Funct Mater* **2023**, DOI 10.1002/adfm.202307109.
- [6] J. Hyun Oh, G. Ho Han, J. Kim, J. Eun Lee, H. Kim, S. Kyung Kang, H. Kim, S. Wooh, P. Soo Lee, H. Won Jang, S. Young Kim, S. Hyun Ahn, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2023**, *460*, 141727.

[7] N. Chen, S. Y. Paek, J. Y. Lee, J. H. Park, S. Y. Lee, Y. M. Lee, *Energy Environ Sci* **2021**, *14*, 6338.